

INTERGATION OF INNOVATIVE PEDOGOGICAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING NATURAL SCIENCES

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ABSTRACT

this article provides information on the effectiveness of the use of innovative educational technologies in the organization of natural science classes.

Keywords: innovative technologies, interactive methods, independent thinking, debating, working with red and green cards.

ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКИХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРОЦЕСС ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ ЕСТЕСТВЕННЫХ НАУК

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АННОТАЦИЯ

В данной статье представлена информация об эффективности использования инновационных образовательных технологий в организации уроков естествознания.

Ключевые слова: инновационные технологии, интерактивные методы, самостоятельное мышление, аргументация, работа с красными и зелеными карточками.

Since Uzbekistan has chosen the way to build a democratic legal state and an open civil society based on a market economy with independence, the new socio-economic relations have set new tasks in terms of content and essence before the educational system, among all areas. The implementation of these tasks assumes regular improvement of the educational system and, through it, deep arming of the younger

generation with the foundations of science. After all, the search for knowledge forms a person's faith and worldview, leads to spiritual and moral maturation.

The method of applying modern pedagogical technology in elementary grades answers the question of what way, by what methods, students will be taught, the result will be effective. It has its own specific system, in which the sequence, correlation, one whole of the components are stored. In a word, with a new approach to the educational process, creativity, creativity are introduced, and the effect of education is brought to a new level. The reader is instilled in me an inner conviction and aspiration that this is necessary and that I am able to know it, to apply it to life.

The introduction of non-traditional classes into natural science classes as well and its absorption into the content of education, the finding of new and new ways of taking classes provides the basis for the fulfillment of the requirements of State educational standards. The role of lessons in Natural Sciences in the comprehension of the human personality in every possible way, giving the growing young generation a good idea of the surrounding world that surrounds it, looking at it through the eyes of love, and getting to know ecology, earth, water, soil, flora and fauna is invaluable. Therefore, we also work with these very goals in organizing our classes.

Education is a long process, the quality of which depends on the methods used in the lesson. The meaningful passage of the lesson, what methods are used in it and the result is achieved, determines the skill, level of knowledge of the teacher. In the lesson, the goal is quickly and easily achieved if the methods are selected correctly. The choice of interactive methods is made based on the didactic purpose of each lesson. This requires the teacher to take a lesson based on methods that are relevant to the topic of the lesson, and not always in the same way. To do this, the teacher must constantly work on himself, improve his knowledge and professional skills, be aware of the news of Science and use them effectively in his activities.

It is known that currently there are more than a hundred types of interactive methods, many of which have passed experiments and gave good results. In our tutorial "innovative technologies in teaching Natural Sciences", which we created, we used the following puzzles:

Let's play the game "fourth Plus" with you, kids. In this game, put 3 + characters on a corresponding picture, one plus – on the icon (Figure 1). Let's get started!

Figure 1. Game “Fourth plus”

By working through this session, students will output 3 overlapping pictures given in the picture and 1 different picture from the rest.

It is up to them that the teacher and the student choose what technology they want in achieving the result from the goal, since the main goal of both parties is aimed at

achieving a specific result, in which the technology used is selected depending on the level of knowledge of the students, the nature of the group and the circumstances.

How the complex of nature depicted in this picture looks from above. Sign + in your correct answer (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Nature complex

By doing this exercise, the student gains a “map” key. They imagine how things seen on a flat plane look on the map.

Method “working with red and green cards”

It is extremely convenient to use this method when working with learners in bulk and group form. The method can be used in the organization of a quick Q & A regarding the strengthening of the topic at the end of training. The method is used on the basis of the organization of the following actions:

according to the number of students of the class, red and green cards and a questionnaire on the topic are prepared by the teacher for each student;

– the questionnaire focuses on the role of questions that can be answered in the “yes” or “no” way;

– red and green cards are distributed to each student;

– students are taught that red cards mean “confirmation”, green cards mean “denial”;

– learners respond to questions posed by the teacher based on the display of cards meaning “confirmation” “or” denial.

The following questions can be asked to students when applying the method “working with red and green cards” in the process of training organized in the 4th grade of general secondary schools in the subject of “Natural Sciences”:

1. The Earth’s level was originally covered with water, in these waters were initially very soda, shellfish-like living beings?
2. Dinosaurs are 50 meters long and 18 meters tall, was it?
3. Due to a fire from meteorites in which dinosaurs fell to Earth broken?
4. Green parts of plants carbon dioxide will it produce?
5. Does the float fins of the fish keep it from drowning?

In conclusion, today’s day is incredibly intense. He demands that each teacher take a creative approach to his work, improve the effectiveness of the lesson using new forms of Education. Especially in natural science classes, the lesson reaches the level of discovery if the student realizes the environment surrounding him, can understand himself and others, the teacher can see his shortcomings and is enthusiastic about correcting them.

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